

“A Peripheral Canon? The Construction of Lesya Ukrainka as a Soviet-Ukrainian Writer”

Abstract

From the birth of the Ukrainian Soviet Socialist Republic (1922), Lesya Ukrainka (1871-1913), along with Taras Shevchenko and Ivan Franko, was part of the central triad of the Ukrainian literary canon. She was thus (re)built as a founding figure of “Soviet Ukrainian identity”. What does this tell us about the role that the Soviet authorities wanted literary cultures from the peripheries of the USSR to play in the framework of their expansionist project?

My study will have a diachronic comparative dimension. I will analyse texts with a biographical dimension, from Mouzychka’s *Lesya Ukrainka’s Life, Social Activity and Poetic Work* (Odessa, 1925) to Deich’s *Lesya Ukrainka* (Moscow, 1954). Based on a comparison with the sources available, when these biographies were written (Ukrainka’s correspondence and her sister’s account of her life), I will analyse the biographical distortions in these texts, with the following aims:

- To analyse how these Soviet biographies claim to “offer” to Ukrainians an author who has been part of the Ukrainian national heritage since before the Revolution.
- To analyse how the literary heritage constructed by Ukrainian intellectuals is transformed into a Soviet peripheral heritage, and what this implies in terms of the manipulation of Ukrainka’s intellectual biography (particularly in the presentation of her Europeanism, her problematic relationship with Ukrainian folklore and her feminist commitment).
- To analyse how Ukrainka’s womanhood, which at the time constituted a gendered periphery (Ukrainka was described as “minor”, “hysterical”, “fragile” and “infantile”), is used to peripheralise Ukrainian culture by analogy.

This study of a biographical corpus will be based on an observation of acts of distortion and concealment of biographical facts. It will also be linked to similar gestures in the context of the philological work of republishing Ukrainka’s texts in the Soviet context: a) deletion of the pre-Soviet prefaces, and a ban on owning editions containing them; b) cuts in the text; c) biased annotations designed to make Ukrainka a pre-Soviet author, and therefore a peripheral writer in relation to Russian centrality (whereas she wants to construct herself as an author of a so-called “non-centralised” Western canon).

I will show that these manipulations define a clearly delimited field of possibilities for Sovietised Ukrainian cultural identity: the Ukrainian canon has the right to exist culturally, but only as a peripheral corpus.

Biobibliographical note

Nikol Dziub is a Swiss National Science Foundation Postdoctoral Fellow at the University of Basel (Chair of East European History) for a research project devoted to Lesya Ukrainka and her posterity in the USSR and post-1991 Ukraine. She holds two Masters degrees (Taras Shevchenko University, Kyiv, Ukraine ; Ecole Normale Supérieure, Lyon, France) and a doctorate in French, general and comparative literature (Université de Haute-Alsace, France, 2015). She has published two essays (*Voyages en Andalousie au XIX^e siècle. La Fabrique de la modernité romantique* [Journées through Andalusia in the 19th Century. The Creation of Romantic Modernity], Droz, 2018; “*Son arme était la harpe*”. *Pouvoirs de la femme et du barde chez Nizami et dans Le Livre de Dede Korkut* [“*Her Weapon was the Harp*.” *The Power of Women and Bards in Nizami’s Works and in The Book of Dede Korkut*], LitVerlag, 2018), edited the correspondence between André Gide and the Petersburg Orientalist of German-Baltic origin Fédor Rosenberg (Presses universitaires de Lyon, 2021, as part of a postdoctoral project on André Gide and the USSR funded by the « Catherine Gide Foundation and Fondation des Treilles Prize »), and co-translated Lina Kostenko’s *Journal d’un fou ukrainien* ([*Diary of a Ukrainian Madman*], L’Harmattan, 2022). A specialist in travel literature, women’s writing, the relationship between literature and imperialism, and representations/constructions of liminal and peripheral spaces, she has edited a dozen collective volumes and published some sixty articles, including (in relation to the subject of her proposal):

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